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Circular SUsustainable FLOor coverings

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D5.2 Overview of standards and certificates applicable to CFC and strategy for further development

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Abbreviations

CFC	Circular Floor Covering
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
ESO	European Standardisation Organisation
EU	European Union
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ePRODIS	Integrated (electronic) Product Information System
(CEN) SABE	(CEN) Strategic Advisory Board for the Environment
TG	Task Group
TC	Technical Committee
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

This document provides an overview of standards, certificates and labels that are already established or in development as they relate to the CISUFLO project. The standards identified address uniform technology, design for recycling guidelines to facilitate the treatment of the product at end-of-life, end-of-life material identification and secondary raw material quality assessment.

The Commission has addressed gaps in standardisation regarding quality of recyclates, design for recyclability and definition of recycled content as part of the deliverables of the Circular Plastics Alliance (CPA) which was initiated in 2019. The result of this work is a standardisation request from the Commission to technical committees within CEN, to deliver relevant standards for specific products and product categories. CEN TC134, covering resilient, textile, laminate and modular multilayer floorcoverings, will be a partner in the execution of the standardisation request. The uniform criteria developed via standards can then be used to develop labels and certification systems that certify that certain products and systems have been produced according to defined standards.

There are more than 455 different certificates and labels relating to sustainability in operation globally. In Europe alone there are 231 labels, 89 of which relate to construction products and buildings. The report focuses on those certificates and labels which relate to products covered by CISUFLO, as well as those that cover recycled content, design for recycling and recyclability.

The sheer volume of labels makes it very difficult for end users, manufacturers and recyclers to identify those that are most relevant to their products and most widely accepted. The report recommends that the criteria which relate to recyclability, recycled content and design for recycling should be added to the Environmental Product Declaration system, which is already widely used within the flooring sector. This would ease the burden on manufacturers and provide end users with one document focusing on the entire lifecycle of a product.

Glossary

European standard (EN): developed by an ESO.

European Standardisation organisation (ESO): CEN, CENELEC, ETSI

International standard: standard developed by ISO.

Standardisation deliverable: standard, technical specification, technical report, work shop agreement, publicly available specification. (In the document will use the expression “standard” for all standardisation deliverables.)

Circular Economy: A systems solution framework that tackles global challenges like climate change, biodiversity loss, waste, and pollution. It is based on three principles, driven by design: eliminate waste and pollution, circulate products and materials (at their highest value), and regenerate nature. *It is underpinned by a transition to renewable energy and materials. Transitioning to a circular economy entails decoupling economic activity from the consumption of finite resources. This represents a systemic shift that builds long-term resilience, generates business and economic opportunities, and provides environmental and societal benefits.*⁽¹⁾

Note: Quite often Circular Economy is abbreviated CE, which is confusing with CE marking. A better way to abbreviate Circular Economy would be C.E.

CE marking: The letters ‘CE’ appear on many products traded on the extended Single Market in the European Economic Area (EEA). They signify that products sold in the EEA have been assessed to meet high safety, health, and environmental protection requirements.⁽²⁾

Note: Construction products put on the market in Europe need to be CE marked.

1 Introduction

This deliverable has been elaborated in the framework of work package (WP) 5, dealing with 'Industrial Uptake'. It relates to task 5.2, dealing with standardisation and certification. This report makes an overview of standards linked to the building, and more specifically, the flooring sector and circular economy/sustainability. Also the topics of uniformity of terminology, communication and end-of-life scenarios and end-of-life material identification are discussed. Standardisation gaps have been identified.

Further, certificates, auditing systems and labels applicable to circular floor coverings are addressed, showing an overview of existing relevant ecolabels. Key initiatives from the European Commission are described like the EU Green Deal and the Circular Plastics Alliance.

This report focusses on the link between CISUFLO's activities and the above mentioned initiatives.

2 Standardisation

2.1 Participation in standardisation committees

Already at proposal stage, several standards and new standardisation projects were identified as highly relevant for circular floor covering. During the CISUFLO project, the publication of standards, development of ongoing standardisation projects and start-up of new projects will be continuously monitored and followed up by the involved CISUFLO partners and associations. Where relevant, CISUFLO will interact with the standardisation committees followed, either to present the results from the project or to inform the project partners on the ongoing developments in standardisation. For this purpose CISUFLO has prepared an updated map of relevant standardisation committees being followed by its members, together with a list of published and standards in preparation.

One important source for identifying relevant CEN Technical committees (TC's) and Working Groups (WGs) is the CEN SABC TG "Circular Economy" that has been established to map all standards having a link to Circular Economy and to develop a standardization strategy to promote Circular Economy and sustainability in general. CISUFLO partners EUFCA and CTB are members of this CEN SABC TG.

The CISUFLO members have identified and are following up the following relevant committees:

1) CEN TC134 "Resilient, textile, laminate and modular mechanical locked floor coverings" (EUFCA, CTB, TFI, UNILIN, BIG)

- WG7 "Resilient floor coverings"
- WG8 "Textile floor coverings"
- WG9 "Laminate flooring coverings"
- WG10 "Harmonization"
- WG11 "Modular mechanical locked floor coverings (MMF)"

A liaison with CEN TC134 has been established on April, 2022. This liaison will allow closer cooperation between the CISUFLO project and CEN TC134, including active participation in the work.

2) CEN TC249 "Plastics" (EUFCA, CTB, EuPC, BIG)

- WG 9 "Bio-based and biodegradable plastics"
- WG 11 "Plastics recycling"
- WG 24 "Environmental aspects"

3) CEN TC249 works closely together with ISO TC61 "Plastics" (CTB, EuPC)

- SC 14 Environmental aspects
 - o WG 1 Terminology, classifications and general guidance
 - o WG 5 "Mechanical and chemical recycling"

4) ISO TC323 "Circular Economy" (EUFCA, CTB, AQUA)

- ISO/TC 323/WG 1 "Terminology, principles, frameworks and management system standard"
- ISO/TC 323/WG 2 "Practical approaches to develop and implement Circular Economy"
- ISO/TC 323/WG 3 "Measuring and assessing circularity"
- ISO/TC 323/WG 4 "Circular Economy in practice: experience feedback"
- ISO/TC 323/WG 5 "Product circularity data sheet"

5) ISO TC38 WG35 "Textiles - Environmental aspects" & CEN TC248 WG39 "Circular Economy for textile products and the textile chain" (CTB, AQUA)

6) ISO TC308 "Chain of custody" (EUFCA)

7) CEN TC350 Sustainability of construction works (EUFCA, CTB, TFI, EuPC)

- SC1: "Circular Economy in the Construction Sector"

8) ISO TC59 SC17 Sustainability in buildings and civil engineering works (CTB, TFI)

Additionally the following committees have been identified as of interest, but which are not followed up via direct participation of a CISUFLO member.

1) ASTM

- E60 - Sustainability

2) GRI (Global Reporting Initiative)

- Global Sustainability Standards Board

2.2 Topics addressed

2.2.1 Uniform terminology

When developing standards or other normative documents, one of the important first steps is to define common terminology to be used in all documents.

For this purpose a committee starting on a new area of standardisation will first establish a document titled “Terms and definitions”, “Vocabulary” or similar. The aim is to use as much as possible available terminology, adapting or developing new terminology only if the existing is too general or otherwise not suitable or non-existing for the new area of standardisation. Several sources exist to find terminology used in standards, a few examples can be found here below:

- ISO online browsing platform (OBP): <https://www.iso.org/obp>
- <https://www.din.de/en/services/terminology>

While terminology concerning plastics recycling and sustainability is already available for several years, the terminology concerning circular economy is still in development. When writing new terminology standards, especially international standards, it is quite challenging to find an agreement on the definitions of the terms as there can be regional differences in interpretation and use of the terms.

Below a (selected) list of published standards and standards in development (terminology):

- ISO 6707-3:2017 Buildings and civil engineering works – Vocabulary – Part 3: Sustainability terms (under revision)
- EN 17228:2019 Plastics - Bio-based polymers, plastics, and plastics products - Terminology, characteristics and communication
- CLC/TR 45550:2020 Definitions related to material efficiency
- FprEN 17615 Plastics - Environmental Aspects – Vocabulary (under publication)
- prEN ISO/CD 5157 Textiles - Environmental aspects – Vocabulary (CEN/ISO)
- prEN 17861 “Resilient, textile, laminate and multilayer modular Floor coverings – Circular Economy – Terms and definitions” (pending CEN Enquiry)
- ISO/WD 59004 “Circular economy – Framework and principles for implementation” (under development)
- WI 00350039 Circular economy in the construction sector – Framework, principles, and definitions (preliminary work item CEN)

2.2.2 Communication

Environmental product declarations (EPD’s) are one of the tools which can be used for communication between different stakeholders. Product circularity data sheets are also valuable tools for communication.

Next to generic standards, also a series of standards and other documents are available for the construction sector (including floor coverings):

- CEN/TR 15941 Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Methodology for selection and use of generic data
- EN 15942 Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Communication format business-to-business
- CEN/TR 16970 Sustainability of construction works - Guidance for the implementation of EN 15804
- EN 15804 Sustainability of construction works - Environmental product declarations - Core rules for the product category of construction products
- EN 16810:2017 "Resilient, textile and laminate floor coverings - Environmental product declarations - Product category rules"
- ISO/AWI 59040 Circular Economy - Product Circularity Data Sheet

2.2.3 End-of-life scenarios

The different options for end-of-life scenarios should be envisioned during the design stage. Circular business models are necessary to support these different end-of-life scenarios.

Below a list of published standards and standards in development (end-of-life) for supporting end-of-life scenarios and circular business models:

- ISO/DIS 8887-2 Technical product documentation — Design for manufacturing, assembling, disassembling and end-of-life processing — Part 2: Vocabulary (under development)
- ISO 8887-1:2017 Technical product documentation — Design for manufacturing, assembling, disassembling and end-of-life processing — Part 1: General concepts and requirements
- prEN ISO/AWI 8887-3 Technical product documentation — Design for manufacturing, assembling, disassembling and end-of-life processing — Part 3: Selection of an appropriate end-of-life design strategy
- WI=00248731 Circular Textiles Chain – Requirements and categories (CEN/TS).

2.2.4 End-of-life materials identification

End-of-life materials identification is an important step for the further re-use/ recycling of materials.

Below a list of published standards and standards in development (materials identification):

- EN 15342:2007 Plastics - Recycled Plastics - Characterization of polystyrene (PS) recyclates
- EN 15343:2007 Plastics - Recycled Plastics - Plastics recycling traceability and assessment of conformity and recycled content
- EN 15345:2007 Plastics - Recycled Plastics - Characterisation of Polypropylene (PP) recyclates
- EN 15347:2007 Plastics - Recycled Plastics - Characterisation of plastics wastes
- CEN/TS 16011:2013 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Sample preparation
- EN 15346:2014 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Characterization of poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC) recyclates
- EN 15348:2014 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Characterization of poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) recyclates
- CEN/TS 16861:2015 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Determination of selected marker compounds in food grade recycled polyethylene terephthalate (PET)
- CEN/TS 16010:2020 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Sampling procedures for testing plastics waste and recyclates
- EN 17410:2021 Plastics - Controlled loop recycling of PVC-U profiles from windows and doors
- EN 15344:2021 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Characterization of Polyethylene (PE) recyclates

- CEN/TS 17627:2021 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Determination of solid contaminants content
- WI00134302 Resilient, textile, laminate and modular mechanical locked floor coverings — Circular Economy and Sustainability — Recommendations/ Guidelines for Design
- WI00134286 “Definition and Declaration of Recyclability and Recycling Potential of textile floor coverings” (preliminary)
- WI00134287 “Definition and declaration of recycled content (organic and inorganic) in textile floor coverings” (active)

There is some overlap of these standards with the secondary raw material quality assessment (see section 2.2.5.)

Different labels and certification schemes utilize standards, please also refer to section 3.

2.2.5 Secondary raw material quality assessment

Secondary raw material quality assessment is important for the (re-)introduction of these materials into the market. For one, all materials used in manufacturing need to be compliant with EU legislation, including e.g. REACH⁽³⁾, as is the case for virgin materials.

Standards for the quality assessment of secondary raw materials are still under development, below a list of standards in development (CEN TC249):

Plastics – Quality requirements for application of plastic recyclates in products

- Part 1: General aspects (PWIWI00249A3K)
- Part 2: Polyethylene (PE) (PWI00249A3C)
- Part 3: Polypropylene (PP) (PWI00249A3I)
- Part 4: Poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC) (PWI00249A3D)
- Part 5: Poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) (PWI00249A3E)
- Part 6: Polystyrene (PS) (PWI00249A3F)
- Part 7: Polyamide (PA) (PWI00249A3G)
- Part 8: Poly(acrylonitrile butadiene styrene) (ABS) (PWI00249A3H)
- Part 9: Polycarbonate (PC) (PWI00249A3J)

2.2.6 Standardisation gaps

The Circular Plastics Alliance (CPA)⁽⁴⁾ was initiated in 2019 to identify standardisation gaps in plastics recycling. Construction products, and specifically floor coverings, were one of the key products identified and analysed. From this initiative the EC developed a standardisation request for plastics recycling and recycled plastics⁽⁵⁾, which is in its finalisation stage at the moment of writing this deliverable. CEN TC249 and CEN TC134 are both involved in the development of the standardisation request and will be partners in its execution.

CEN TC350 SC1 “Circular Economy in the Construction Sector” is also performing a gap analysis for construction products. Their work started in 2022 with establishing a first preliminary work item:

- WI00350039 Circular economy in the construction sector – Framework, principles, and definitions (preliminary)

The CISUFLO project is not following CEN TC350 directly, but is informed via its liaison with CEN TC134 (which has a liaison with CEN TC350).

CISUFLO also aims to identify any additional standardisation gaps not covered and will bring these forward in the technical committees in which CISUFLO experts are involved.

3 Certification, auditing systems and related labels

The Ecolabel Index (ecolabelindex.com), the largest global directory of ecolabels, lists 455 ecolabels in 199 countries and across twenty-five industries. In Europe alone there are 231 ecolabels listed of which 89 are linked to buildings and building products.

The labels are aimed at various audiences including corporate purchasers, retailers, consumers, manufacturers, specifiers, and designers. Some certify products, others certify companies or organisations. They are all based on a varying number of national, international or European standards.

Many of them are based on ISO14021:2016 Environmental labels and declarations - Self-declared environmental claims (Type II environmental labelling) or ISO 22095:2020 Chain of custody - General terminology and models, defining the approach taken to control inputs and outputs and associated information in a particular chain of custody system, for example to track recyclates from the end-of-life of a product right through their use in a new product.

The sheer number and complexity of environmental certificates and labels makes it difficult for manufacturers as well as end users of products to navigate their way through.

This report focuses on labels and certification schemes which relate to recycled content, design for recycling or traceability of materials through the supply chain. It looks at certifications and labels relevant to plastics, textile, and wood in line with the products that are part of the CISUFLO project.

Traceability of recyclates through the supply chain is becoming increasingly important as we move from a linear economy to a circular economy in Europe, where the EU Green Deal launched by the Commission in 2019 is driving change on a systemic level. For this purpose, several new approaches are being developed and tested, including an incorporation of the blockchain technology into the existing tracing techniques.

The EU Green Deal is the key initiative of the European Commission to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 and to decouple economic activity from the consumption of finite resources. A large number of policies, legislations and initiatives have grown from this vision since 2019. Recycled content requirements are a key for the development of circular systems and reuse of resources and many of the initiatives currently under consideration by the EU, focus on minimum recycled content targets. This includes the proposed revision of the Construction Products Regulations, which foresees in Article 22 the obligation to declare mandatory sustainability characteristics, including minimum recycled content.

Table 1 highlights some of the certifications and labels that are currently operating in Europe and globally which look at recycled content and lifecycle assessment of products. It also covers sustainability certifications and labels that apply to textile floorcoverings, wood, and plastics.

Table 1 Overview certification, auditing systems and related labels

Name	Focus	What is targeted	Target audience	Related Standards	Area of operation
AENOR	Recycled Plastics Traceability and Recycled Plastic Content .	Plastic products containing recyclates	Manufacturers, end users	UNE EN 15343Plastics plastics - Traceability in plastics recycling and evaluation of conformity and recyclates content	Spain
Blue Angel	The Blue Angel has been the ecolabel of the German federal government for more than 40 years. It is awarded to environmentally friendly products and services. It is an independent label that certifies products in a product group based on a comprehensive range of criteria such as Resource-conserving production (water, energy, (recycled) materials), sustainable production of raw materials, avoidance of pollutants in products, reduced emissions of harmful substances into the soil, air, water and indoor spaces, reduction of noise and electromagnetic radiation and efficient use and products that use a low level of energy or water.	Products	Consumers	ISO 14024 “Environmental labels and declarations - Type I environmental labelling - Principles and procedures (ISO 14024:2018)”.	Germany
CRI Green Label Plus	In 1992, the Carpet and Rug Institute (CRI) launched its Green Label program to test carpets, cushions, and adhesives to help specifiers identify products with very low emissions of VOCs. This enhanced program sets the standard for indoor air quality.	Textile floor coverings	Retailers		USA

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<p>DIN CERTCO</p>	<p>Certification programme for plastic product made from recycled material. The certification focuses on the evaluation of the system for traceability and for calculating the recycled content in the plastic product. DIN CERTCO uses auditors recognised by it to conduct the necessary audits as a basis for the assessment and certification of the products.</p>	<p>Plastic products</p>	<p>Plastic products</p>	<p>ISO 1402 1 Environmental labels and declarations - declarations (Type II environmental labelling) DIN EN 15343 Plastics plastics - Traceability in plastics recycling and evaluation of conformity and recyclates content DIN EN 15342 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Characterisation of polystyrene(PS) recyclates DIN EN 15344 Plastics - Plastic recyclates - Characterisation of polyethylene(PE) recyclates DIN EN 15345 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Characterisation of polypropylene (PP) recyclates DIN EN 15346 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Characterisation of polyvinyl chloride (PVC) recyclates DIN EN 15347 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Characterisation of waste plastics DIN EN 15348 Plastics Recycled plastics - Characterisation of polyethylene terephthalate (PET) recyclates DIN EN 71-3 Safety of toys - Part 3: Migration of certain element</p>	<p>Germany</p>
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EcoVadis	EcoVadis - company sustainability reporting. EcoVadis sustainability assessment methodology is an evaluation of how well a company has integrated the principles of Sustainability/CSR into their business and management system.	Company sustainability reporting	companies and organisations		Global
EPD Environmental Product Declaration	The EPD provide relevant, verified, and comparable information to meet various customer and market needs. In an EPD manufacturers report comparable, objective and third party verified data that show the environmental performance of their products and services. It provides product specific LCA data.	Products	Manufactures, end users	ISO 14025: Environmental labels and declarations, ISO 14040 Environmental management: Lifecycle assessment principles and framework, For the construction sector ISO 21930 – Sustainability in Building construction, EN 15804 +A2 Sustainability of construction works – Environmental product declarations	Global
EucertPlast	Traceability of plastic materials (throughout the entire recycling process and supply chain) and quality of recycled content in the end-product.	Plastic recyclates	Recyclers operating according to high standards and implementing best practice	EN 15343:2007 Plastics - Recycled Plastics - Plastics recycling traceability and assessment of conformity and recycled content	EU

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<p>EU Eco label</p>	<p>EU Eco labels are attached to products that meet the environmentally friendly criteria determined by official institutions, associations, or certification bodies. These criteria are determined on the basis of the environmental impact of the product's life cycle and on the basis of extensive scientific research. Eco labels focus on certain environmental aspects of products. It covers many environmental aspects, for example energy consumption, water use, timber resource, and so on. Eco labels have a different structure than green symbols and environmental claims. Eco-labelled products are evaluated and verified by an independent and impartial third party. As a result of these studies, the products are guaranteed to meet certain environmental performance requirements.</p>	<p>Products</p>	<p>Consumers</p>	<p>Life cycle assessment standards</p>	<p>EU</p>
<p>FSC</p>	<p>The Forest Stewardship Council® (FSC) promotes environmentally appropriate, socially beneficial, and economically viable management of the world's forests. FSC® chain of custody (CoC) tracks FSC certified material through the production process - from the forest to the consumer, including all successive stages of processing, transformation, manufacturing, and distribution. Only FSC CoC certified operations are allowed to label products with the FSC trademarks. The FSC label provides the link between responsible production and consumption and enables the consumer to make socially and environmentally responsible purchasing decisions.</p>	<p>Wood</p>	<p>Corporate purchasers, government purchasers, consumers, retailers, specifiers, and designers</p>	<p>FSC-STD-40-004 V2-1 EN Chain of Custody Standard</p>	<p>Global</p>

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GRI - Global reporting initiative	The Global reporting standard develops standards which enable sustainability reporting providing information on an organisations positive or negative contribution to sustainable development.	Sustainability performances of companies and organisations, not material specific	Companies and organisations	Global reporting initiative develops its own reporting standards. the GRI Universal Standards, which apply to all organizations; the GRI Sector Standards, applicable to specific sectors; and the GRI Topic Standards, each listing disclosures relevant to a particular topic.	Global
GUT	The aim of GUT is to improve continuously all environmental and consumer protection aspects throughout the life cycle of a textile floor covering (from production to installation, to use phase and recycling).	Textile floor coverings	Consumers, retailers, specifiers, and designers	Life cycle assessment standards	EU
ISO 2600: Corporate Social Responsibility	Corporate Social responsibility standard. It provides guidance rather than requirements, so it cannot be certified to unlike some other well-known ISO standards. Instead, it helps clarify what social responsibility is, helps businesses and organizations translate principles into effective actions and shares best practices relating to social responsibility.	Company sustainability reporting	Companies and organisations		Global
Plastica Seconda Vita	Plastica Seconda Vita is an environmental product certification system dedicated to materials and products obtained from the recycling of plastic waste; It covers quality and traceability of recycled materials.	Plastic Products containing recyclates	Manufacturers, end users	EN ISO 14021	Italy

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QACer	QACer assures the quality system related to the recycling process and use of recycled materials. Both the recycled content and the quality of the end product are addressed in order to support the principle of sustainability.	Recycled products	Industrial companies that produce polymer recyclates and/or use them in extrusion processes.	ISO 9001 forms the basis; EN 15347 Plastics - Recycled Plastics - Characterisation of plastics wastes; EN 15343 used to define: a traceability system for polymer waste flows	EU
RAL GÜTEZEICHEN	RAL is an assurance make that benchmark technical requirements, for the process stages of the recyclable material chain of PET beverage packaging, with the expressed goal to increase the amount of recyclates in PET beverage	Plastic PET beverage packaging	Producers, end users		EU, Germany
RecyClass	<p>RecyClass is a technical cross-industry initiative that works to advance plastic packaging recyclability and to establish a harmonized approach towards recycled content calculation and traceability in Europe. Activities within RecyClass include the development of Recyclability Evaluation Protocols and scientific testing of innovative materials which serve as the base for updating the Design for Recycling guidelines and the free online tool. Furthermore, RecyClass develops and maintains certification schemes for plastic packaging recyclability and for recycled content traceability in plastic products.</p> <p>RecyClass activities focus on giving a detailed and personalised assessment to companies to improve the recyclability of their plastic packaging and to integrate recycled plastics in their plastic products.</p>	Certification system for plastic packaging recyclability.	Packaging Products	ISO 22095: Chain of custody — General terminology and models EN 15343:2007: Plastics. Recycled plastics. Plastics recycling traceability and assessment of conformity and recycled content	EU

All these labels either look at the lifecycle of products using lifecycle assessment standards, or they look in particular at ensuring and certifying the quality and contents of recyclates in products placed on the market.

This is important with regard to the Circular Plastics Alliance (CPA), a Commission initiative to encourage industry to pledge the use of ten million tonnes of recycled plastics in new products placed on the market in the EU by 2025.

These targets require robust auditing and certification schemes to verify recycled content and ensure quality of recyclates. Standards define how to calculate the content and define quality and certification and audit schemes serve to verify the correctness of claims made by the manufacturers.

The Circular Plastics Alliance has set up a monitoring system to monitor the flow of recyclates from the recycler to their use in new products at the convertor site. The CPA has approved two platforms for collecting data in compliance with the CPA monitoring rules and methodology

- MORE, managed by EuPC, collecting data only on the use of recycled plastics - <https://www.moreplatform.eu>
- RecoTrace managed by PolyREC, collecting data on both the production and use of recycled plastics - <https://recotrace.com/auth/login>

MORE – Monitoring Recyclates for Europe is an EU harmonized digital platform to monitor the uptake of recycled polymers into products. It collects data for use of recycled plastics in the form of a survey from converters. RecoTrace collects data for both the recycling and the use of recycled plastics.

In order to provide traceability of the data collected via MORE, EuPC has set up the PolyCert Europe, which facilitates the verification and auditing of the volumes reported into the MORE platform. PolyCert Europe is an umbrella technical platform set up to harmonise existing certification schemes for converters of polymeric materials in Europe. The idea behind the system is to bring together national accredited certification bodies from all over Europe to harmonise the calculation of recycled content in new products. Currently it covers QA-CER, Plastica Seconda Vita, RAL Gütezeichen, DIN CERTCO and AENOR (see Table 1). This approach ensures that converters can be certain of the quality of recyclates they obtain and ensure that the way to calculate recycled content across different national certification schemes is the same.

Given the sheer number of certification and labels that are present in Europe, this approach helps the manufacturers of products to navigate their way through the system and to ensure consistent messaging with regard to recycled content.

4 Conclusions and strategy for the future

In conclusion, there are already a large number of standards, certificates and labels available, both globally and in Europe. It makes sense for floorcoverings to fit into one of the existing schemes but based on a clear understanding of the terms and definitions as they apply to floorcoverings. This will help to reduce costs for manufacturers and make the communication of the quality and recycled content clearer. Environmental Product Declarations are widely used in the flooring sector. It would make sense to utilise this system to also provide information on the quality and design for recycling specifications of a given product, based on the product standards being developed in this field.

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